

High Resolution Computed Tomography Lung Spectrum in Symptomatic Adult HIV Positive Patients: A Hospital-Based StudyShikha Rani¹, Rajiv Kumar²¹MBBS, MD (Radio-diagnosis), Senior Medical Officer (SMO), Guru Govind Singh Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Professor & Head, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Netaji Subhas Medical College & Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Shikha Rani

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objectives:** The present study was to evaluate the high-resolution computed tomography lung spectrum in symptomatic adult HIV positive patients.**Methods:** General physical and respiratory system examination of all patients was done. Then a meticulous record of all the available laboratory investigations including HIV status, CD4 counts, routine blood examination, sputum examinations, pleural fluid analysis, FNAC, and other available investigations was kept. Chest x-rays of the patients were studied for the presence of any abnormality. HRCT scans of the chest were done using mentioned HRCT protocol. The patient was kept supine on the gantry table and was scanned cephalocaudal in the axial axis. Scans obtained with patients' supine were adequate in most instances. Prone scans were taken when needed. The scanogram or to pogram was first taken and then the whole lung was scanned from apex to the base. The scans were performed on Siemens Somatom Emotion 16 Slice Multidetector scanner.**Results:** Out of 30 cases of HIV positive patients, most of cases were males 21(70%). Majorities of the cases 11(36.67%) were in age group of 18 to 30 years. 8(26.66%) cases were in age group of 31 to 40 years. 21(70%) cases were diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis followed by 5(16.67%) bacterial infection. And 4(13.33%) cases had not significant abnormalities. Out of 21 pulmonary tuberculosis cases, 14(66.67%) cases were nodular opacities. HRCT pattern in bacterial infections cases were lobar Consolidation 3(60%), nodular opacity and bronchiectasis 1(20%).**Conclusions:** HIV positive cases were greatly seen in young age male population. Pulmonary tuberculosis was the most common clinical manifestation of HIV positive cases. Scans with Single finding and two findings, and three findings, nodules, Consolidation with pleural effusion, and nodules with cavitation with GGO with lymphadenopathy were the common HRCT pattern. Centrilobular with tree in bud, clustered with centrilobular with tree in bud, centrilobular and random were the common nodular distribution. Lobar Consolidation, nodular opacity and bronchiectasis were the common HRCT pattern of bacterial infection in HIV positive patients. Hence, HRCT is one of the best choice of investigations of lungs parenchyma in symptomatic HIV positive patients.**Keywords:** HIV positive, HRCT pattern, Lung spectrum.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Tuberculosis (TB) is the commonest and most devastating infectious disease in a HIV positive patient especially in developing nations. It has also been proven that the greatest risk of a person acquiring tuberculosis is HIV positivity, more so in endemic countries like India [1].

It is therefore wise to consider opportunistic infection with tuberculosis in HIV positive individuals and vice versa. In addition to the usual rising curve of tuberculosis incidence worldwide, the past few years have seen significant propulsion

in this rise after the advent of HIV. An estimate of over 34 million individuals was affected with HIV in a 2013 report by World Health the Organization (WHO) [2]. In 2010, the estimated prevalence of TB infected HIV patients were 14 million signifying almost 50% individuals being coinfecting with TB and HIV [3].

Tuberculosis remains the forerunner leading to death of HIV infected individuals and in India, TB-HIV co-infection is reported to be around 38% [4]. The delay in diagnosis results in delay in

therapy with more chance for spread of infection and increase in severity of the disease [5]. Findings on computed tomography (CT) have been used to accurately diagnose pulmonary complications of AIDS[6]. During the current era of HIV, radiographic findings may differ in light of the decreasing incidence of pulmonary infections, but few studies have re-examined radiographic findings on chest CT examination in the contemporary population[7].

Given the frequency of chronic respiratory complaints in HIV infected populations [8,9] and the high prevalence of CT scanning[10], understanding radiographic manifestations of HIV is important for patient care.

HRCT is helpful in the differential diagnosis of TB from other lung diseases, in the distinction of active from inactive TB, in determining the degree of smear positivity, and in assessing antituberculous treatment efficiency [10]. HRCT has some demerits such as added cost and higher radiation as compared to chest X-ray, but in equivocal or indeterminate cases it can identify active tuberculosis even if the chest radiograph is negative. Objectives of our study was to evaluate the high-resolution computed tomography lung spectrum in symptomatic adult HIV positive patients.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Guru Govind Singh Sadar hospital, Patna city, Patna, Bihar during a period from September 2022 to January 2023. A total of 30 HIV positive patients were enrolled based on following inclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- HIV positive adult (>18 years) patients of both sexes who have presented with a lung disease on the basis of clinical profile and plain radiography.

Exclusion Criteria

- Immunocompromised patients who have suspected lung
- Disease but are HIV negative. Pregnant HIV positive patients. The primary clinical features were weight loss, fever, cough (both productive and non-productive) and dyspnoea.

Methods

A thorough clinical history of all the HIV positive patients presenting with suspicion of pulmonary disease was taken. Duration of symptoms was also

recorded. General physical and respiratory system examination of all patients was done.

Then a meticulous record of all the available laboratory investigations including HIV status, CD4 counts, routine blood examination, sputum examinations, pleural fluid analysis, FNAC, and other available investigations was kept.

Chest x-rays of the patients were studied for the presence of any abnormality. HRCT scans of the chest were done in all the cases taken in the study.

Patient Preparation

The procedure and objectives of performing the high-resolution CT scan was explained to the patient. Prior fasting was not advocated as the procedure did not warrant the need for contrast injection. The patient was explained and demonstrated the procedure of breath holding during the acquisition of HRCT scans.

HRCT protocol

Patient Position

The patient was kept supine on the gantry table and was scanned cephalocaudal in the axial axis. Scans obtained with patients' supine were adequate in most instances. Prone scans were taken when needed. The scanogram or to pogram was first taken and then the whole lung was scanned from apex to the base. The scans were performed on Siemens Somatom Emotion 16 Slice Multidetector scanner using the following protocol. Collimation = 1 mm Feed = 10mm Scan time = 1 sec KVp = 120 – 140 mA = 240 Matrix size = 512 x 512 Windows-window mean/ width values = -600 to -700/ 1000 to 1500

Reconstruction Algorithm

High spatial frequency algorithm was used. It reduces image smoothening and increases spatial resolution, making structures appear sharper. Thus, small vessels and bronchi are better seen in HRCT.

Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed by using of simple statistical methods with the help of MS-Office software. All the data was tabulated, percentages were calculated.

Results

In the present study, out of 30 cases of HIV positive patients, most of cases were males 21(70%) and 9(30%) were females. Majorities of the cases 11(36.67%) were in age group of 18 to 30 years. 8(26.66%) cases were in age group of 31 to 40 years.

Figure 1: Gender wise distribution of HIV positive patients

Table 1: Age wise distribution of HIV positive patients (N=30)

Age group (Years)	No. of patients	Patients
18-30	11	36.67%
31-40	8	26.66%
41-50	6	20%
51-60	3	10%
61-70	2	6.67%
Total	30	100%

In the present study, out of 30 HIV positive cases, 21(70%) cases were diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis followed by 5(16.67%) bacterial infection. And 4(13.33%) cases had not significant abnormalities. Among the pulmonary tuberculosis cases, HRCT pattern of majorities of cases were Scans with Single finding 4(19.05%), nodules

3(14.28%), Scans with two findings 4(19.05%), Consolidation with pleural effusion 3(14.28%), Scans with three findings 6(28.57%), Scans with four findings 2(9.52%) and Nodules with cavitation with GGO with lymphadenopathy 2(9.52%). The CD4 count in these patients varied from 22 to 398 cells/mm³ with a mean count of 192 cells/mm³.

Table 2: HRCT Patterns and their frequency in Pulmonary Tuberculosis cases (N=21)

HRCT Findings	No. of patients	Percentage
Scans with Single finding	4	19.05%
Nodules	03	14.28%
Lymphadenopathy	01	4.76%
Scans with two findings	04	19.05%
Consolidation with nodules	01	4.76%
Consolidation with cavitation	01	4.76%
Consolidation with pleural effusion	03	14.28%
Nodules with pleural effusion	01	4.76%
Scans with three findings	6	28.57%
Consolidation + nodules + lymphadenopathy	01	4.76%
Consolidation + nodules+ pleural effusion	01	4.76%
Consolidation+cavitation+nodules	01	4.76%
Consolidation+Nodules +GGO	01	4.76%
Nodules + lymphadenopathy	01	4.76%
Nodules+ lymphadenopathy+pleural effusion	01	4.76%
Nodules+ GGO+ pleural effusion	01	4.76%
Scans with four findings	02	9.52%
Nodules+consolidation+cavitation+lymphadenopathy	01	4.76%
Nodules+cavitation+ GGO+ lymphadenopathy	02	9.52%

In the present study, out of 21 pulmonary tuberculosis cases, 14(66.67%) cases were nodular opacities. Nodules distribution of most of the tuberculosis cases were centrilobular with tree in bud 5(35.71%), clustered with centrilobular with tree in bud 4(28.57%), centrilobular and Random 2(14.29%).

Table 3: Nodules distribution in TB cases (N=14)

Distribution of nodules	No. of patients	Percentage
Centrilobular	02	14.29%
Centrilobular + Tree in bud	05	35.71%
Clustered +Centrilobular +tree in bud	04	28.57%
Random	02	14.29%
Clusters	01	7.14%

In the present study, HRCT pattern in bacterial infections cases were lobar Consolidation 3(60%), nodular opacity and bronchiectasis 1(20%). The CD4 count in these patients varied from 119 to 362 cells/mm³, with a mean count of 197cells/mm³.

Table 4: HRCT patterns and their frequency in bacterial infection (N=5)

HRCT Findings	No. of patients	Percentage
Lobar Consolidation	03	60%
Nodular Opacity	01	20%
Bronchiectasis	01	20%

Discussions

Respiratory manifestations predominate the list of opportunistic infections in patients with HIV, Tuberculosis (TB) is the commonest and most devastating infectious disease in a HIV positive patient especially in developing nations. It has also been proven that the greatest risk of a person acquiring tuberculosis is HIV positivity, more so in endemic countries like India [1]. It is therefore wise to consider opportunistic infection with tuberculosis in HIV positive individuals and vice versa. In addition to the usual rising curve of tuberculosis incidence worldwide, the past few years have seen significant propulsion in this rise after the advent of HIV.

Tuberculosis remains the forerunner leading to death of HIV infected individuals and in India, TB-HIV co-infection is reported to be around 38% [4]. An interesting fact is that people with HIV develop TB infection well before the drop of CD4 count below 400 500 is ironic [6]. Due to this reason, the WHO has recommended antiretroviral therapy initiation for all HIV infected patients who develop tuberculosis irrespective of their CD4 count [2].

The adult HIV prevalence (males and females together) in India, in 2009 is estimated as 0.31% with uncertainty bounds 0.25–0.39%. Gender wise, HIV prevalence was estimated at 0.25% for women and 0.36% for men [11]. Our study also supported the above findings, (70%) cases weremales because they are sexually more active and the social structure is patriarchal. Females do not seek medical care fearing ostracism and loss of family support. In the present study, HIV positive cases were more seen in young age populations.

In the present study, out of 30 HIV positive cases, 21(70%) cases were diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis followed by 5(16.67%) bacterial infection. The World Health Organization (WHO) reported that among the 9.27 million incident cases of tuberculosis, an estimated 14.8% occurred in

HIV-positive patients, with 456,000 deaths from tuberculosis among HIV-infected patients [12]. The African region accounted for most HIV-positive tuberculosis cases (79%), followed by the Southeast Asia region (mainly India), which had 11% of total. According to NACO annual report 2012-2013 “fatality rate among HIV infected TB cases remain 13-14% against less than 4% in HIV negative TB cases” [12]. Computer Tomography (CT) is considered the gold standard for assessing the morphological changes of lung parenchyma [13]. In the present study, Among the pulmonary tuberculosis cases, HRCT pattern of majorities of cases were Scans with Single finding 4(19.05%), nodules 3(14.28%), Scans with two findings 4(19.05%), Consolidation with pleural effusion 3(14.28%), Scans with three findings 6(28.57%), Scans with four findings 2(9.52%) and Nodules with cavitation with GGO with lymphadenopathy 2(9.52%).

Hilar and mediastinal lymph node enlargement is commonly seen on HRCT in patients who have active tuberculosis. Mediastinal lymphadenopathy is more commonly seen in HIV-positive patients as compared to HIV-negative patients who present more commonly with lung parenchymal opacities and cavitations [14]. In the study by Feng et al., the presence of lymphadenopathy was a significant finding in which lymphadenopathy could be observed in 44 (77.2%) of 57 patients with TB [18]. Pleural effusion is a common complication in pulmonary tuberculosis. Effusion is mostly exudative in nature. Unilateral effusion is more common than bilateral. In study of 3263 patients with definite or suspicious TB, Taiwan, 24.27% had tuberculosis pleurisy [15].

In the present study, nodular opacities were seen in 14(66.67%) cases. Nodules distribution of most of the tuberculosis cases were centrilobular with tree in bud 5(35.71%), clustered with centrilobular with tree in bud 4(28.57%), centrilobular and Random 2(14.29%).

TB lymph nodes are typically markedly enlarged and of low attenuation on CT. Patients with lower CD4 count have an increased incidence of miliary TB, with diffuse, randomly distributed nodules on CT, as found in the study of Keiper et al [16].

Hatipoglu et al., observed that centrilobular nodular or linear structures (91%), “tree-in-bud” appearance (71%) and micronodules (69%) were the most common HRCT findings seen in active pulmonary tuberculosis [17]. Feng et al., showed that weight loss, miliary nodules, necrotic lymph, lobar consolidation, and tree-in-bud sign were independent predictors for AIDS-related PTB [18].

In the study by Naseem et al., HRCT findings included centrilobular nodules in 92% cases, lobular consolidation in 84%, cavitation in 76%, and ‘tree-in-bud’ appearance in 68%, lymphadenopathy in 8% and military nodules in 4% cases [19].

In the present study, HRCT pattern in bacterial infections cases were lobar Consolidation 3(60%), nodular opacity and bronchiectasis 1(20%).

Allen et al.[20] reported that abnormalities may be detected on HRCT in the absence of any CXR findings these include bronchiectasis and evidence of small airway disease, with ill-defined centrilobular micronodularity and branching structures or tree-in-bud appearance secondary to mucus impaction in the bronchioles. Mosaic attenuation may also be present due to air trapping.

Magenat et al., and Boisselle et al., reported that focal consolidation was observed in approximately 45-60% of patients with pyogenic infection [21,22]. Selwyn et al., found that the combination of focal consolidation of chest radiography and a history of fever for fewer than seven days were associated with a sensitivity of 48% and a specificity of 94% for the diagnosis of bacterial pneumonia [23]. In the present study, CD4 count of bacterial infections cases varied from 119 to 362 cells/mm³, with a mean count of 197 cells/mm³. Opportunistic infections commonly occur among AIDS patients in developing nations, bacterial pneumonias are more common in AIDS patients in developed countries [21,24]. In India, due to the burden of tuberculosis, bacterial agents are second common in causing lung infections. Streptococcus pneumonia followed by Haemophilus influenzae is the commonly associated community pathogens [25].

Rarely occurring pathogens causing community acquired pneumonia are Legionella pneumophila, Mycoplasma pneumoniae and Chlamydia pneumoniae [25]. Since, the advent of AIDS, the spectrum of clinical presentation has broadened as disseminated infections are being reported.

Dissemination occurs when there is a drop of CD4 count below 50 cells/mm³ [26].

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the HIV positive cases were greatly seen in young age male population. Pulmonary tuberculosis was the most common clinical manifestation of HIV positive cases. Scans with Single finding and two findings, and three findings, nodules, Consolidation with pleural effusion, and nodules with cavitation with GGO with lymphadenopathy were the common HRCT pattern. Centrilobular with tree in bud, clustered with centrilobular with tree in bud, centrilobular and random were the common nodular distribution.

Lobar Consolidation, nodular opacity and bronchiectasis were the common HRCT pattern of bacterial infection in HIV positive patients. Hence, HRCT is one of the best choice of investigations of lungs parenchyma in symptomatic HIV positive patients.

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